

Quasielastic Neutron Scattering Reveals Anisotropic Water Transport in Smectite Thin Film

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Clay minerals exhibit complex interactions with water that critically influence their functional properties, yet the anisotropic nature of water dynamics in smectite thin films remains underexplored. Here quasielastic neutron scattering (QENS) is employed on oriented sodium beidellite films to investigate water mobility across multiple timescales and orientations. Analysis reveals pronounced anisotropic water dynamics, characterized by confinement perpendicular to the clay layers and orientation-dependent diffusion coefficients and residence times. These dynamics correlate with structural features, including interlayer cation spacing and anomalies in the hydroxyl group absorbance. The findings elucidate directional transport and confinement phenomena in layered smectites, providing fundamental insights that can guide the design of clay-based materials with tailored transport and interfacial properties.

1. Introduction

Clay minerals are essential components of soil and are widely used industrial materials, making them a focus of research across disciplines ranging from geology and soil stability to biochemistry and catalysis.^[1–3] Central to their functionality is a detailed understanding of surface interactions with water;^[4,5] such interactions are ubiquitous in natural systems and play a critical role in the high reactivity and tunable properties of industrial clays. Confined water significantly influences chemical and mechanical properties, structural organization, and ion-exchange capacity of these materials, making its study particularly relevant for

applications such as water purification, drug delivery, and CO₂ capture.^[6–8]

Clay minerals possess a complex layered structure, and among the 2:1 layer-type, dioctahedral smectites are particularly important due to their broad industrial relevance and therefore the most extensively studied. Dioctahedral smectites are hydrous aluminosilicates with negatively charged layers resulting from isomorphic substitution, where Al³⁺ is partially replaced by Mg²⁺ in the octahedral sheet, and Si⁴⁺ is replaced by Al³⁺ in the tetrahedral sheet. The resulting negative charge is balanced by hydrated,^[9] exchangeable cations in the interlayer space **Figure 1a**). Traditional techniques such as X-ray diffraction (to monitor interlayer spacing),^[10,11] adsorption isotherms (to assess hydration state),^[12] thermogravimetric analysis (to estimate activation energies)^[13] have contributed to valuable structural and thermodynamic insights. However, these methods lack the resolution to probe water dynamics at atomic and molecular scales, where key structure–function relationships emerge. To overcome these limitations, quasi-elastic neutron scattering (QENS) has gained increasing importance in clay mineral research, offering unmatched sensitivity to hydrogen dynamics over time scales from femtoseconds to nanoseconds and length scales of 1–100 Å.^[8,10,14–20] A summary of the neutron scattering basic theory is developed in the **Figure S1** (Supporting Information).

Observation of a quasi-elastic signal in the measured dynamic structure factor, $S(Q, \omega)$ (**Figure 1b**) is attributed to water relaxation dynamics in the hydrated clay and normally modelled using Lorentzian functions. The evolution of the extracted half-width at

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half-maximum (HWHM, hereafter $\Gamma(Q)$, Figure 1c) as a function of momentum transfer (Q) defines the nature of the described motion. Assuming a jump diffusion, it is possible to distinguish if the molecule repetitively undergoes an oscillatory motion for a mean time τ_0 and then diffuses with a coefficient D_t .^[21] In addition, it is possible to identify the mechanism or process of the motion detected. For simple reorientations, i.e., Γ is independent of Q , and an isotropic rotation model can be used in which the water molecules rotate on a sphere with radius r , about all possible axes without preferred orientation (Figure 1d).^[22] If the water molecules undergo a translational diffusive motion (Figure 1e), either the two-site jump or the confined diffusion will equally well describe the geometry of the motion.^[23] However, for diffusion confined within a spherical volume of radius R , the two-site jump model defines the distance, d , between two sites during random jumps (Figure 1f).^[24] A full description and representation of the models used is given in the [Supporting Information](#).

For hydrated clay minerals, modelling QENS data enabled the distinction of various water populations within clays, including: i) structural hydroxyls, ii) interlayer water coordinated to exchangeable cations, iii) secondary interlayer water associated with neighbouring molecules, iv) water loosely hydrogen-bonded to clay surfaces, and v) interparticle water.^[26] However, the forms of interlayer water (ii through iv) undergo a hydration-state dependent continuum of dynamic exchange with time scales larger than nanoseconds (ns).^[27,28] Characteristic relaxation times can also be advantageously estimated from the peak of the susceptibility spectrum, $\chi''(Q, \omega)$ (Figure 2a), in which any two well-separated relaxation processes appear as two distinct peaks and can be easily compared with other experimental techniques used to study relaxation phenomena.

While previous studies have demonstrated that anisotropic effects in oriented clay films can be analysed,^[16,29–32] most investigations of water dynamics in smectites have relied on isotropic powder samples. This approach overlooks directional transport and confinement phenomena that are critical for understanding and engineering the functional behaviour of layered materials. Both layer charge distribution and OH orientation influence the mobility of interlayer water. To address this gap, we recently investigated the anisotropic water dynamics in sodium beidellite (Na-Bd), a dioctahedral smectite with layer charge predominantly located in the tetrahedral sheets, arising from substantial Al^{3+} for Si^{4+} substitution (0.8–1.0 per formula unit), and minimal $\text{Mg}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ substitution in the octahedral sheet.^[29] Thus, in beidellites, the negative charge is located near the in-

terlayer surface, where hydrogen-bonded water resides, suggesting the possibility of a stronger coupling between charge localization and water mobility compared to other smectites like montmorillonite, in which the charge originates mainly from the octahedral layer and thus ≈ 0.4 nm from the surface. To explore how these charge-structural differences affect water dynamics across relevant timescales, we extended our previous work by performing QENS measurements on oriented Na-Bd films (Figure 2c). Experiments were carried out using two complementary spectrometers, AMATERAS and DNA, at the Materials and Life Science Experimental Facility (MLF) at J-PARC, Japan.^[33,34] By combining data analysis from these instruments, we accessed an extended time window of 70–200 ps (0.07–0.2 ns) on the same sample, enabling a more detailed investigation of local environmental influences on translational diffusion of interlayer water. This multiscale approach provided critical insight into direction-dependent dynamics, essential for designing advanced functional materials with tailored transport properties.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Distinguishing Non-Localized (Diffusive) Motions in the Oriented Films

Figure 3 reveals two distinct relaxation processes, both exhibiting Q -dependent behaviour. This observation is also reflected by the need for two Lorentzian functions to fit the data, as shown in Figures S2 and S3 (Supporting Information).

First, a distinct fast response is seen centred ≈ 500 GHz (≈ 2 meV or 2 ps), which, regardless of sample orientation, becomes progressively less defined at high Q -values. This attenuation is primarily attributed to two factors: i) the neutron scattering cross section contains a $1/\omega$ dependence, leading to reduced intensity with increasing frequency (ω) and momentum transfer (Q); and ii) geometrical effects, particularly enhanced absorption of incident neutrons at larger Q -values.^[29] The second, distinct Q -dependent relaxation appears as a tail extending to ≈ 100 GHz (≈ 0.4 meV or 10 ps), most prominently observed for $Q = 1 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ as illustrated in Figure 3b. This signal indicates the presence of another non-localized, diffusive motion occurring on the time and length scales probed by the instrument. The existence of such diffusive dynamics in the oriented films is further confirmed through analysis of the QENS broadening (half-width at half-maximum, HWHM) as a function of Q^2 .

Figure 1. a) Schematic illustration of the 2:1 layer structure of dioctahedral smectites detailing relationships between tetrahedral and octahedral sheets, smectite layers, and interlayer containing water molecules and exchange cations. The distance between the clay layers is given by the distance d , which is obtained from the [001] reflection. This value defines the number of water molecules in the sample. Exchangeable cations (black ball) neutralize the negative layer charge and interact with variable amounts of water molecules, which can move in parallel and perpendicular directions within the interlayer. In this set of pictures, the blue spheres represent hydrogen atoms, the red spheres represent oxygen atoms, and the grey lines between hydrogen and oxygen atoms represent covalent bonds. The black lines between oxygen are not bonds but represent the edges of polyhedra (i.e., tetrahedra and octahedra). Images modified from.^[25] b) Representation of the measured dynamic structure factor, $S(Q, \omega)$, obtained for Na-Bd using AMATERAS. c) Representation of the evolution of the quasi-elastic signal as a function of momentum transfer, Q , for Na-Bd. The increase in elastic intensity for $Q = 1.4 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ is due to the presence of a Bragg reflection. d) Isotropic rotation of a H_2O molecule with a radius of rotation, r . e) Representation of the two-site jump model for H_2O with two sites separated by the distance, d . f) Depiction of translational diffusion of H_2O within a sphere of variable radius, R , related to confinement. A full description of the models is given in the [Supporting Information](#).

Figure 2. a) Susceptibility spectra, $\chi''(Q, \omega)$, of Na-Bd at different Q-values for $\varphi = 55^\circ$, showing a clear shift of both faster and slower dynamics to higher energy on increasing Q. b,c) Schematic illustration of the definition of the rotation of the orientated clay films in relation to the incident neutron beam. The set of grey dashed lines represents the thin film sample, NaBd-GWC30%. The incident neutron beam \vec{k}_i is marked in blue, and 2θ defines the angle between \vec{k}_i and \vec{k}_f (marked red). The sample is rotated by the angle φ (marked in green). (b) In the perpendicular (PP) configuration, the sample holder is rotated by an angle of 45° , such that the scattering vectors \vec{Q} are oriented mostly perpendicular to the clay layers. (c) In the parallel (PL) configuration, the sample holder is rotated by an angle of 135° , such that the scattering vectors \vec{Q} are oriented mostly parallel to the clay layers.

Figure 3. Susceptibility spectra, $\chi''(Q, \omega)$, of Na-Bd at different orientations for a) $Q = 0.4 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ and b) $Q = 1.0 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$. From this figure, the water in this sample presents two dynamics that are well separated in time. The dashed line in (a) is a guide to the eye only. The slower motion (below 0.01 ns) is highlighted by the grey area in (b).

Figure 4. Evolution of the narrower quasi-elastic broadening Γ vs Q^2 obtained from DNA a) and AMATERAS b,c) with 45°, 60°, and 100° orientation corresponding to the diffusive motions described in the text and Table 1. Note the plateau-like behaviour at small Q -values for the 100° orientation. Evolution of the $EISF_1$ vs Q obtained from DNA (a) and AMATERAS e,f), corresponding to a combination of motions as described in the text and Table 1.

2.2. Disentangling a Complex Mixture of Slower (Γ_1) and Faster (Γ_2) Water Dynamics in the Oriented Films

The evolution of $\Gamma_{\text{DNA-45}}$ vs Q^2 for the 45° orientation (hereafter Γ_1) is illustrated in Figure 4a, and an example of fitted data is shown in Figure S4 (Supporting Information). This data can be modelled using the expression for the Singwi–Sjölander (SS)^[35] model. The EISF calculated for the same data ($EISF_1$) is better fitted using the confined diffusion model as depicted in Figure 4d using Equations S11,S12 and S15 (Supporting Information). A jump length, l , of ≈ 4 Å, a residence time, τ_0 , ≈ 50 ps, a diffusion coefficient, D_i , of $0.6 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, and 50% immobile water molecules were obtained from the best fit.

For sample orientations between 55° and 100° (Figure 4b,c), the two Lorentzian functions fitted to the AMATERAS data exhibited distinct behaviours: one was a narrow, high-intensity function, while the other was broad and of low intensity. This result is taken as indicative that two discrete water populations were

probed. Due to the large differences in energy resolution of the two spectrometers, only the slower dynamics describing a more constricted mobility were detected using DNA, and thus, the narrower contribution observed using AMATERAS can be attributed to the same relaxation process assigned to Γ_1 . On the other hand, the second component observed with AMATERAS, hereafter Γ_2 , can be assigned to a less confined water population. For 55°, 60°, 70°, and 85°, the evolution of Γ_1 vs Q^2 was also successfully described using the SS model (Figure S5, Supporting Information), which corroborated our assumption that the same slow motion attributed to the confined water was probed. However, at small Q -values, Γ_1 approaches a plateau for 100° (Figure 4c), indicating that at this orientation, water motions were too slow to be fully probed in the resolution of AMATERAS. This behaviour was previously observed in other systems.^[36] Finally, as also illustrated in Figure S5 (Supporting Information), the SS model can be used to effectively fit the evolution of $\Gamma_{\text{DNA-135}}$ vs Q^2 for the 135° orientation (Γ_1).

Table 1. Summary of all parameters describing the narrow Lorentzian (Γ_1). The equations defining the models are given in the Supporting Information. Between 55° and 100°, the co-fitting of Γ_1 is described by p_1 and r_1 , describing a confined diffusion contribution, while p_2 and d_2 are ascribed to a two-site jump contribution. This implies that the fraction of water molecules undergoing confined diffusion is given by $f_1 = (1 - p_1)$, while those displaying two-site jump diffusion correspond to $f_2 = (1 - p_2)$. The remaining immobile fraction is then $f = (1 - f_1 - f_2)$. For comparison, D_t and τ_0 for bulk water are $2.3 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 1.25 ps.^[37,38]

Sample orientation	45°(DNA)	55°	60°	70°	85°	100°	135°(DNA)
Γ_1 vs Q^2	Singwi-Sjölander model (SS) ²⁰						
τ [ps]	44.2	10.8	15.4	9.2	8.4	1.1	48.1
D [$10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$]	0.58	1.0	1.6	1.0	0.9	0.4	0.72
	Combination confined diffusion and of two-site jump						
p_1	0.5	0.7	0.9	0.85	0.85	0.86	
r [Å]	8.7	8.3	12.3	12.0	12.5	14.1	
f_1	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.15	0.15	0.14	
p_2		0.6	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2
d [Å]		5.1	5.3	5.2	5.3	5.1	12.1
f_2		0.4	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.8
f	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.15	0.15	0.16	0.8

Turning to the analysis of the EISF_1 vs Q (Figure 4d–f and Figure S6, Supporting Information), a combination of confined diffusion and a two-site jump model, described by Equation S16 (Supporting Information), was necessary to adequately fit the data across all orientations measured on AMATERAS. Corresponding fit parameters are given in Table 1. As the angle of rotation increased, the fraction of immobile water molecules (f) decreased, reaching a minimum near 60°. While the jump distances remained the same ($d \approx 5$ Å), the diffusion radius r increases from 8 Å at 55° to 14 Å at 100°, indicating that a greater number of protons participate in this type of motion within the probed timescale probed likely due to the availability of a larger dynamic volume. Notably, the observed jump distances correlate closely with the average cation-cation distances calculated for the Na-Bd interlayer (dashed arcs in Figure 5).

If we consider that H-bonded water will jump from locations between interlayer cations to equivalent locations, the resulting distance, as the average of the first two shells, is ≈ 8.8 Å. This increases to ≈ 15 Å if the average of the 2nd and 3rd shells is taken and ≈ 12 Å if all three shells are averaged. This can be understood considering that perfect parallel (PL) and perpendicular (PP) alignments of the scattering vector- Q relative to the clay layers occur only at specific angles. Therefore, we can hypothesize that the observed deviation reflects anisotropic sampling of the water dynamics in the oriented Na-Bd films. Such a result implies that below a film angle of 60°, shorter jump distances in the PP direction are preferentially probed, while at higher film angles, longer jump distances in the PL direction can be accounted for. Since in beidellite (Bd) the layer charge is primarily located in the tetrahedral sheets, the O–H vectors of structural OH groups—associated with octahedral Al—are expected to be oriented at steep angles ($>55^\circ$) relative to the ab plane,^[39] which means that the structural OH have an opposite anisotropy to the observed anisotropic behaviour of interlayer water.

A summary of the analysis of Γ_1 as a function of Q^2 for all sample orientations is shown in Figure 6a,b. This graphic representation revealed clear variations in both the translational diffusion coefficient (D_t) and the residence time (τ_0). In agreement

with the evolution of EISF_1 vs Q , a crossover is also observed at 60° in Γ_1 vs Q^2 . A maximum D_t value of $1.6 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ observed at 60° strongly supports the presence of anisotropic water dynamics and indicates that the signal originated predominantly from hydrogen-bonded interlayer water, rather than structural hydroxyl groups.^[40] Additionally, the longer residence times observed at 45° and 135° suggested that the dynamics were dominated by water molecules directly coordinated to interlayer cations. This is likely due to the higher energy resolution and narrower observable energy window of the DNA spectrometer, which enhanced sensitivity to slower motions.^[20,27] The plateau observed at lower Q -values of Γ_1 , instead of approaching zero as would be in the case of spatially unconfined diffusion, observed

Figure 5. Average distances between interlayer cations overlaid the unit parameters of Na-Bd, assuming parameters used by Bleam.^[25] The model considers charged layer potentials from both interlayer surfaces. The dashed arcs correspond to average distances between “shells” of neighbouring interlayer cations (the black circular pattern), the square box is the unit cell dimensions, the red circles are the repeat positions of the unit cell, the black circles are average sites of equidistant interlayer cation (in this case sodium, Na) and the dashed arches represent the average distances of nearest and next-nearest neighbour cation shells.

Figure 6. Changes in translational diffusion coefficient, D , with sample orientation a) and changes in residence time, τ_0 , with orientation b) in confined water. Both D and τ_0 attained maximum values between 55° and 60° .

at 100° , may also be attributed to such slower dynamics that cannot be resolved.

Turning now to the analysis of the broader Lorentzian Γ_2 , one observes that between 55° and 70° orientations (Figure 7a) that the QE broadening remained nearly constant with Q . Its value ≈ 0.2 meV corresponded to a residence time $\tau_0 \approx 1.6$ ps, which was slightly larger than the residence time reported for bulk water 1.25 ps at 20°C ,^[38] suggesting a shorter average lifetime of H-bonds in the clay–water system. The analysis of EISF₂ (Figure 7d) was performed using two models: one describing isotropic rotational motion and another representing diffusion within a confined spherical volume (Equations S13 and S15, Supporting Information).

The results indicate that localized motion occurs within a radius of ≈ 1.8 Å at the two lowest sample orientations, increasing to ≈ 2.3 Å at 70° , suggesting a less restricted environment at higher angles. A more significant finding is the evolving behaviour of the fast water at increased orientation angles of 85° and 100° (Figure 7b,c). Analysis of the 85° data with the SS model was successful, yielding a diffusion coefficient of $D = 3.9 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Such a result indicated that this water population, probed at a strongly PL direction, moved significantly faster than bulk water,^[37] with $\tau_0 = 1.4$ ps. Similarly, faster water diffusion has been observed in studies on hydrophobic membranes.^[32] Therefore, we can argue that in this work, independent of orientation, the faster water molecules are potentially influenced by the Na–Bd layer charges. However, for the 100° orientation, the water molecules exhibited free diffusion with a value close to that of free water. One hypothesis to explain this observation is that we have identified interlayer water of type (iii), as described in,^[26] associated with surface regions between sites of isomorphic substitution. In beidellites, the structural charge is less diffusely distributed across the surface,^[41,42] reducing the likelihood that sur-

face oxygen atoms in these regions can participate in hydrogen bonding. Another possibility is that this water is type (iii) and is located between the hydration shell of the interlayer cation and the water molecules hydrogen-bonded to the clay surface. While the oxygen atoms in type (iii) water tend to form hydrogen bonds with the hydrogen atoms of the cation-bound water, its own hydrogen atoms cannot easily bond with either the oxygen atoms of surface-bound water or the clay surfaces themselves. Both configurations would place type (iii) water in an energetically excited state compared to bulk water. The results are summarized in Table 2.

3. Conclusion

Despite the critical importance of diffusion coefficients for estimating transport properties in clay minerals, their characterization has remained limited due to experimental and theoretical challenges.^[32,43] Here, we change this landscape by directly probing the complex anisotropic dynamics of interlayer water in oriented Na-beidellite thin films through a combination of quasielastic neutron scattering, modelling, and structural analysis. Our results reveal direction-dependent diffusion behaviour, with accurate values of diffusion coefficients and residence times extracted across different clay orientations. Specifically, measurements at 45° and 135° (relative to the neutron beam) yield significantly lower diffusion coefficients than bulk water, confirming the presence of tightly bound cationic water. Additionally, the diffusion coefficient for H-bonded water populations is highest between 55° – 60° , indicating anisotropic confinement effects. Considering the high degree of layer alignment and excluding interparticle water contributions, this anisotropy is consistent with the interlayer environment of Bd. The observed jump distances match well with Na–Na and

Figure 7. Evolution of Γ_2 vs Q^2 a–c) and EISF₂ vs Q d,e) obtained from AMATERAS corresponding to either localized or diffusive motions described in the text and Table 2. Results for 55° orientation (shown in Figure S7, Supporting Information) that overlap with those for 60° were omitted for clarity. Note the interesting Γ_2 variation as a function of orientation.

hydrated cation spacings,^[25] suggesting limited contributions from structural OH groups (Figure 6). Moreover, the strong electrostatic potentials arising from interlayer cations and isomorphous substitution are likely correlated with these dynamics.^[19,20] At higher angles (70°–85°), the emergence of confined diffusion regimes further highlights the directional nature of interlayer water transport. These findings provide fundamental insights into the nanoscale transport phenomena in smectites and lay the groundwork for designing advanced clay-based materials with tailored functionalities.

4. Experimental Section

Obtaining Highly Oriented NaBd Films: The sodium form of the <0.2 μm fraction of the source clay beidellite SBCa-1 (Na-Bd, Clays Repository, The Clay Minerals Society) was extracted by sedimentation and centrifugation.^[30] Oriented self-supporting films (each ≈100–200 μm

thick, prepared by vacuum deposition) were prepared by dispersing ≈1 g Na-Bd in ≈15 mL deionized water in 20 mL glass test tubes, capped and agitated using a vortex for several minutes. The sample was then set aside to fully hydrate for three days before being re-agitated for 10 min, three times during a 2-h interval. A portion of the sample volume was then transferred using a Pasteur pipette onto as many as three locations of a clean mylar film, which had the desired sample size (40 × 45 mm) previously delineated. The films were then allowed to dry under ambient conditions. Petri-dish covers (propped up to allow air flow) were placed over the films to keep them clean while drying. Once dry, the clay films were carefully separated from the mylar film. The weight of each resulting self-supporting film was recorded after drying to oven-dry equivalency using a moisture analyser (HC103, Metler Toledo), and then an amount of deionized water was added to each film using a micro pipette to achieve 30 wt.% water content. The samples were then placed into waxed weighing paper sleeves and enclosed in two zip-sealed plastic bags to physically protect the films, to minimize water loss, and to ensure that the samples were hydrated by surface water and water confined within the interlayer.^[14] Because of the paper sleeves, the hydration state of the clay was ultimately somewhat

Table 2. Summary of all parameters describing the broader Lorentzian (Γ_2) only observed in the AMATERAS data between 55° and 100°.

Sample orientation	55°	60°	70°	85°	100°	
Γ_2 vs Q^2	Rotation					
	meV	0.2049				
	τ_0 [ps]	0.19440.2186				
	Singwi-Sjölander model (SS) ²⁰					
	τ [ps]	1.6	1.7	1.5		
	D [$10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$]				1.4	
	Translational diffusion					
D_t [$10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$]					2.0	
EISF ₂ vs Q	Isotropic rotation					
	P_{iso}	0.6	0.6	0.70		
	r_{iso} [Å]	1.7	1.8	2.3		
	Confined diffusion					
	p				0.70	0.68
	r [Å]				3.7	3.7

less than 30 wt.%. Details about the calculation of the number of water molecules in the Na-Bd film are given in the [Supporting Information](#). For the neutron scattering experiments, stacks of two or three films of each sample (total film thickness $\approx 500 \mu\text{m}$) were placed into a flat aluminium sample holder securely sealed. The sample mass/thickness was chosen to achieve sufficiently high total scattered intensities but to avoid corrections for multiple scattering. A picture from the sample mounted in the container used for the experiments is shown in [Figure 2b](#).

Combining AMATERAS and DNA: Observing confined water dynamics in a broad observation time AMATERAS is a high flux, cold-neutron multi-resolution direct time-of-flight spectrometer,^[33] whereas DNA^[34] is a near-backscattering spectrometer featuring a chopper cascade that enables flexible instrument configuration through the use of Si(111) analysers. Both spectrometers are installed at the Spallation Neutron Source at the Materials and Life Science Experimental Facility (MLF) of J-PARC, Japan. Owing to the high peak intensity from an H₂-coupled moderator source and the use of fast disk choppers for pulse shaping as well as monochromatizing the neutron beam, AMATERAS provides for high intensity and variable energy resolution. Here, the data were collected with a wavelength of $\lambda = 5.2 \text{ \AA}$, energy $E_i = 3 \text{ meV}$, and energy resolution $\Delta E = 54 \mu\text{eV}$, allowing covering relaxation times in the range of 70 ps and a momentum transfer, Q , ranging from 0.4 to 1.6 \AA^{-1} , corresponding to distances between 4 and 16 Å. For DNA, the slit opening phases enabled the scanning of an energy transfer, δE , between -20 to $100 \mu\text{eV}$, giving an energy resolution at the elastic line of $3.5 \mu\text{eV}$.¹³ This configuration corresponded to an observation time between 40 and 200 ps and a Q -range between 0.08 and 1.98 \AA^{-1} , covering a real space distance of 3 to 80 Å.

The intrinsic resolution function of the spectrometers, $R(Q, \omega)$, was defined, and the data were calibrated using a vanadium standard, an entirely elastic and isotropic material.

Sample Orientation and Data Reduction: Data were collected at 300 K, and the sample holder containing the stacked clay films was rotated about the incoming neutron beam, k_i , as shown in [Figure 2](#). During the AMATERAS data collection, five different orientations were measured by rotating the sample holder to various angles (45°, 55°, 60°, 70°, 85°, 100° and 135°). For DNA, data were collected at 45° and 135° since at these orientations the dynamics were too slow to be detected by AMATERAS. With the sample holder rotated by an angle of 45°, Q is oriented mostly perpendicular (PP) to the clay layers to the clay layers, while at 135° the scattering vector Q is oriented mostly parallel (PL) to the clay layers.

Data was processed using the UTSUSEMI reduction program,^[44] where it was calibrated against a vanadium run, and the background was ad-

justed based on measurements from the empty cell. Since NaBd was crystalline, for AMATERAS, the detectors containing Bragg reflections were discarded, and the remaining spectra were grouped to obtain seven constant scattering vectors with an equal spacing of 0.2 \AA^{-1} . However, a minor contribution from the strong [001] reflection at $d \approx 15.7 \text{ \AA}$, corresponding to $Q = 0.4 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ could still be observed. Additionally, the feature at $Q = 1.2 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ ($d \approx 4.4 \text{ \AA}$ is likely caused by residual anatase, which exists in the bulk material and is often challenging to separate. For the DNA data, every three data points were grouped to achieve a consistent width of 0.15 \AA^{-1} . Due to the geometry of the sample holder, DNA data has a shadow for the PL orientation in the Q -range between 0.575 and 1.225 \AA^{-1} , while for PP, the presence of a Bragg reflection made it difficult to analyse the data above 1 \AA^{-1} , see [Figure S8](#) (Supporting Information). However, these issues did not adversely impact the analysis of the data since the detectors related to this response were discarded. Data were converted into the dynamic structure factor $S(Q, \omega)$, where ω corresponds to the energy transfer. This function primarily reflects the movement of hydrogen atoms as detected within the spectrometer observation window. The uncertainties for $S(Q, \omega)$ were estimated based on Poisson statistics.

Data Analysis: The measured $S(Q, \omega)$ can be divided in an elastic contribution, modelled by a delta function, $\delta(\omega)$, describing the structural and immobile hydrogen and a quasi-elastic signal, attributed the water relaxation times modelled by Lorentzian functions, $L(Q, \omega)$, convoluted to the resolution function, $R(Q, \omega)$ of the instrument that defines the observation time as defined by Equation 1.^[21]

$$S(Q, \omega) = \left[\left(\text{EISF}(Q) \delta(\omega) + (1 - \text{EISF}(Q)) \sum_{i=1}^n L_i(Q, \omega) \right) \right] \otimes R(Q, \omega) + B(Q) \quad (1)$$

$B(Q)$ is a background term originating from motions that are too fast to be probed by the spectrometer, and EISF is the elastic incoherent structure factor defined in Equation 2.

$$\text{EISF} = \frac{I_{\text{el}}}{I_{\text{el}} + I_{\text{QE}}} \quad (2)$$

where I_{el} and I_{IN} denote the integrated elastic and inelastic intensity. This definition encompasses all the dynamical processes of the scattering particle being analysed.^[21,24]

Based on this, the data were analysed using the DAVE software^[45] using either one (DNA, 45° and 135° orientation) or two (AMATERAS, all other orientations) Lorentzian functions. The χ^2 values obtained from the AMATERAS data are given in the [Table S1](#) (Supporting Information). From the fitting results, the half-width at half-maximum (HWHM) for the Lorentzian was obtained as a function of Q^2 as well as the EISF for each orientation. These parameters were modelled using Matlab2018a, The MathWorks, Natick, MA.

Additionally, the imaginary part of the susceptibility (analogous to mechanical or dielectric loss spectra), was obtained using the following expression:

$$\chi''(Q, \omega) \propto \frac{S(Q, \omega)}{n_B(T, \omega)} = S(Q, \omega) * \left[e^{\omega/kT} - 1 \right] \quad (3)$$

where, $n_B(T, \omega)$ is the temperature Bose factor.

Statistical Analysis: As neutron scattering experiments are inherently counting experiments, the uncertainty of the data is defined by Poisson statistics $\delta N = \sqrt{N}$, where N is the number of counts in each frequency bin. Hence, the fractional error is $\frac{\delta N}{N} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}$. To ensure a high signal-to-noise ratio, measurement times ranged from 4 to 8 h. The χ^2 (chi-squared) test was used as the statistical analysis tool for goodness-of-fit. The results are presented as Supplementary material together with the graphical representations of the fits.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

anisotropic water dynamics, clay–water interactions, quasielastic neutron scattering (QENS), smectite thin films

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